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AUTHOR NAME(S): Çağatan Taşkın

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1. Executive Summary

This report (D4.3) is about the business model innovation activities and their impacts on the hospitality companies. The report includes the introduction part that explains the purpose and connection with the other deliverables such as D4.1 and D 4.2. It also gives detailed information about the methodology applied in the REMODEL project called BUU Business Model Innovation Lab Approach. Firstly, the framework of business model innovation is explained. In other words, business model innovation methodology is designed. It is an eight step methodology that worked in all companies. In addition, the tools that are used in the process of business model innovation are explained. Especially, business model canvas, value proposition canvas, SWOT analysis, action learning approach are used.

Information about the pilot round of the business model innovation implementation and second round of the business model innovation implementation is given for each hotel company. In this part, implementation strategies of business model innovation are clarified for each hotel. As seen from each hotel work, business models of all of the hotels are innovated. In the last part of the report, impact assessment is done according to the two-step impact assessment methodology. This methodology includes focusing on the early indicators and results of semi-structured interviews with the owners. According to the impact assessment results, business model innovation methodology has been successful for the hotels. The evidences are presented in the related part of the report.

2. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to present the impacts of business model innovation methodology on hotels. As proposed in the REMODEL project, there are two other

reports related to this report. These reports are D 4.1 and D 4.2 deliverables. Turkish hospitality industry is analyzed in D4.1 report. In D 4.2, business model innovation methodology and its stages are explained in detail. In other words, the first deliverable takes the picture of the Turkish hospitality industry and the second deliverable gives information about the methodology of how to innovate the business models of the companies. Thus, D 4.3 deliverable gives evidences of the impacts of the implemented business models. We can say that these three deliverables complement each other. The first deliverable includes a situation analysis in terms of qualitative and quantitative perspectives. The second deliverable shows the methodology of how to innovate business models. Finally, third deliverable gives information about the implemented business models although the project has a limited time.

3. Development of Innovative Business Models

3.1. Methodology Applied (BUU BMI Lab Approach)

- Framework of business model innovation

BMI Lab uses an eight-step methodology to analyse the hotel and innovate its business model. Information is given about the stages, tasks and aims of the BMI Lab methodology.

Figure 1. BMI Lab methodology

1st Stage: Preliminary Assessment

Aim: To analyse the general profile of the hotel and competitors

Tasks: Review of the Hotel's Website

Review of the Hotel's Social Media Accounts

Analysis of comments and complaints (Google and TripAdvisor)

Analysis of the Competitors

2nd Stage: Experiencing the Hotel Services

Aim: To experience all the customer journey stages by BMI Lab staff

Tasks: Informing the Hotel Manager about this stage

Experiencing one-night accommodation and recording the observations by means of service blueprint

Preparing a report about this customer journey

3rd Stage: *Introducing the REMODEL Project to all of the managers and Making Situation Analysis*

Aim: To inform all the managers about REMODEL Project and BMI Lab Methodology

Tasks: Presenting the REMODEL Project to all the managers and getting feedback

Explaining BMI Lab Methodology to the managers

Understanding the expectations of the managers

Determining the work schedule

Aim 2: To make a situation analysis

Tasks: Collecting qualitative data for SWOT analysis

Collecting qualitative data for Value Proposition Canvas

Collecting qualitative data for Business Model Canvas

4th Stage: *Analysis and Consolidation of All Collected Data*

Aim: To analyse all collected data and consolidate for BMI tools

Tasks: Visualization of SWOT analysis

Visualization of the Value Proposition Canvas

Visualization of the Business Model Canvas

5th Stage: Idea Generation

Aim: To generate innovative/transformational ideas based on the data analysed

Tasks: Using brainstorming to generate innovative/transformational ideas

Placement of Ideas in the Innovation Matrix and Evaluation

Placement of Ideas in “The Four Type of Innovation in Business” Graphics and Evaluation

6th Stage: *Presentation of the Ideas to Hotel Management*

Aim: To introduce the generated ideas to the managers of the hotel and to get feedback

Tasks: Presenting the ideas

Informing about the positive effects of the ideas

Getting feedback from the managers

Determining the idea/s that should be implemented

7th Stage: *Determining the Implementation Stages of the Selected Idea/s*

Aim: To determine implementation stages of the selected idea/s

Tasks: Determining the elements that need to be changed/transformed in the Hotel in order to implement the selected idea/s

Designing the Value Proposition Canvas according to the selected idea/s

Designing the Business Model Canvas according to the selected idea/s

8th Stage: *Presentation of the Implementation Stages of the Selected Idea/s to Hotel Management*

Aim: To explain how to implement the stages of the selected idea/s

Tasks: Presenting the implementation stages

Presenting the Value Proposition Canvas

Presenting the Business Model Canvas

Evaluation of the implementation stages with hotel management

- Tools used for business model innovation

As mentioned in the BMI lab methodology, swot analysis, value proposition canvas and business model canvas are planned to be used. Thus, the interview questions are designed according to these BMI tools. Before designing the interview questions, a few meetings were held with the hotel's owner and employees. The aim of these meetings was to explain BMI Lab Methodology to the managers and the employees, to understand the expectations of the managers and to determine the work schedule. After these meetings, interview questions were designed and qualitative data was collected.

The interview question form is composed of three parts which are "questions about swot analysis", "questions about value proposition canvas" and "questions about business model canvas".

Questions for SWOT Analysis:

- Who is your target segment?
- Can you give information about your customer profile?
- Do you have any customer records, databases or documents?
- What are the strengths of your Hotel?
- What are the weaknesses of your Hotel?
- What are the opportunities for tourism market?

- What are the threats for tourism market?

Questions for Value Proposition Canvas:

- What are the expected benefits of your customers from your hotel?
- What exceeds their expectations?
- What do your customers aim to have in your hotel?
- What are the obstacles for your potential customers that prevent them from staying at your hotel?
- What are your services and your unique selling proposition?
- What do you do in order to make your customers get their expected benefits?
- What are the precautions for the things that lead to customer dissatisfaction during the accommodation?

Questions for Business Model Canvas:

- How do your customers communicate with your hotel?
- What are the communication problems of your customers with your hotel?
- What do you do in order to keep and manage customer data and information?
- How do you use your customer data and information for offering services?
- What are the reservation channels that your customers use?
- What are the benefits and difficulties of using agencies? What are the roles of agencies?
- What are the key activities for value creation?

- What are your key activities that make you unique?
- What are your key activities that make your customers prefer you?
- What are your stakeholders/business partners?
- What is the contribution of your business partners to your value proposition?
- What do you do in order to manage and continue the relations with your business partners?
- What are the resources that are important for your hotel?
- What is the contribution of the resources to your value proposition?
- How do you manage the resources in order to keep the value proposition and make it sustainable?
- What are your cost elements?
- How do you manage these cost elements?
- Are there any cost elements that you can decrease without a having a negative impact on value proposition?
- What are your income generating methods?
- How do you diversify your income generating activities?

After these studies, a workshop has been planned in order to generate ideas that will innovate the business model of the hotel. In the workshop, action learning method is adopted. Here is a brief explanation of action learning. Action learning is an approach to individual and organizational development. (Pedler, 2008:3). One of the key contributions of action learning is to create a culture of inquiry and questioning, which is an essential aspect of the learning organization. Action learning is a voluntary approach. The Organisational Readiness Survey can be used to determine whether an organisation or individual is ready for action learning. Based on the score, it can be

decided whether the Action Learning approach is appropriate for your organisation or not.

Reg Revans is considered to be the father of the Action Learning approach, which has been adapted worldwide. According to Revans, he formulated this approach as follows:

$$L=P+Q$$

In this equation, L represents learning and is directly influenced by programmed knowledge (P) and questioning (Q). In addition, learning should also outpace change within the organisation. According to Revans, the crucial stage of this formula is the questioning part. Only by asking the right questions can you get the answers, and therefore self-learning and self-awareness can be established.

With the action learning approach there are some critical elements which are the set, the facilitator, the members of the set and above all the wicked problem. Pedler (2008) explain wicked problem as "problems that have no right answers and are approached by people in different ways through the exercise of questioning insight". In addition, the role of the set members and the facilitator is of utmost importance within the action learning set. The facilitator creates the set, sets the ground rules, informs set members about the process and enables psychological safety within the set. The diversity and commitment of the set members has a direct impact on the quality of the action learning outcome. Set members should focus on the problem solver, listen carefully and contribute only by asking questions. Set members should not see the action learning as an arena to humiliate the issue holder.

The facilitator should also make sure that this does not happen within the set. Set members should meet for a set period of time and at the end of the process make sure

that an action plan is placed for the wicked problem. Revans (2011) said that "there is no learning without action and no (sober & deliberate) action without learning".

3.2. First Round Implementation (3 Pilot Hotels)

- Developed business models and implementation strategies

Three hotels were selected for pilot stage implementation. These hotels are Oksijen Zone Hotel, Gököz Natural Park and Artıç Hotel. Three of them are located in Bursa. Different business models are developed for each hotel. Business models and implementation strategies are explained briefly here.

3.2.1. Oksijen Zone Hotel

The business model of Oksijen Zone Hotel is examined in detail up to this part. The critical part of the study is about finding the answers to the question of "how to innovate the business model". It is beneficial to give a definition about business model and business model innovation here. While business model is about how to do business, business model innovation is about how to do business in new/better ways. Here is the figure of business model. Business model innovation can also be defined as the process of value creation while changing the current business model or adapting an innovative approach. In other words, any positive change in a business model means business model innovation.

When it is looked at the current business model, the main problem is that Segmentation-Targeting-Positioning (STP) strategies of the hotel were not clear. Thus, a new segmentation study is conducted in order to understand the market. First, tourism market for Oksijen Zone is divided into two main segments that are called

winter and summer segments. Each segment is analysed according to the customer database and divided into various sub-segments as seen from the figures.

Winter segmentation is based on the duration of accommodation. In the classification, “one-night” means one-night accommodation, “low” means 2-3 days accommodation and “moderate” means 4-6 days accommodation.

Figure 2. Oksijen Zone Segment 1

Under winter segment, Oksijen Zone Hotel&Spa should target these four segments respectively but should change value propositions for each sub-segment.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Oksijen Zone Hotel&Spa should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Oksijen Zone Hotel should mention these: (Possible USP's can be a peaceful winter holiday experience for families. / a charming experience in nature)

- Best location for ski-slope (ski-run)
- Quality food&beverages
- Peaceful hotel for families
- Mini Club for children
- Spa/salt room

- Activities/games for adults and children (including night)

Summer segmentation is based on the duration of accommodation. In the classification, “one-night” means one-night accommodation, “low” means 2-3 days accommodation and “moderate” means 4-6 days accommodation.

Figure 3. Oksijen Zone Segment 2

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Oksijen Zone Hotel&Spa should have a different positioning strategy for summer segment. Under summer segment there are two different types of sub-segments. One of them consists of domestic tourists while the other one consists of business tourists. Here, business tourist can be defined as SME’s and Universities. As mentioned before, summer season of Uludağ was defined as the time period from April to October. The weather gets very hot especially in the summer months. As Uludağ is a mountain area, Oksijen Zone Hotel will be the best place for working camps, meetings of SME’s and University researchers in Marmara region which mainly covers İstanbul, Eskişehir and Balıkesir cities.

So, positioning strategy of Oksijen Zone Hotel&Spa for the summer segment should be different for these sub-segments.

Business Segment

- Nature and cool weather
- Healthy environment
- Boost creativity
- Best motivation for your employees
- Local and organic food
- Relaxation
- Making group connections

Turkish Families

- Best place to discover nature
- Healthy environment
- Local organic food
- Activities for children

USP: Discover the nature, motivating employees

3.2.2. Gököz Natural Park

When it is looked at the current business model, the main problem is that Segmentation-Targeting-Positioning (STP) strategies of the hotel were not clear. Thus, a new segmentation study is conducted in order to understand the market. First, tourism market for Gököz Natural Park is divided into two main segments that are called winter and summer segments.

Winter segmentation is based on the interview conducted with the hotel's owner.

Figure 4. Gököz Segment 1

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Gököz Natural Park should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Gököz Natural Park should mention these: (Possible USP's can be a peaceful winter holiday experience for families in the nature/ a romantic ambiance for couples)

- Great mountain and lake view
- Quality food&beverages
- Peaceful hotel for families
- Romantic ambiance for couples
- Sincere service/Feel like home
- Activities/games for adults and children

Summer segmentation is based on the interview conducted with the hotel's owner.

Figure 5. Gököz Segment 2

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Gököz Natural Park should have a different positioning strategy for summer segment. Under summer segment there are two different types of sub-segments. One of them consists of adventurists who enjoy various activities while the other one consists of corporate groups. Here, corporate groups can be defined as businesses, sports clubs and educational institutions. Since the weather gets very hot especially in the summer months in Türkiye in general, Gököz Natural Park will be the excellent place for working camps, meetings of corporate groups in Marmara region which mainly covers İstanbul, Eskişehir and Balıkesir cities as Gököz Natural Park is established near the mountain area.

So, positioning strategy of Gököz Natural Park for the summer segment should be different for these sub-segments.

Corporate Groups

- Nature and cool weather
- Healthy environment
- Boost creativity

- Best motivation for your employees
- Local and organic food
- Relaxation
- Making group connections

Adventurists

- Best place to discover nature
- Various activities
- Local organic food
- Adventure
- Cool weather

USP: Discover the nature, motivating employees

3.2.3. Artıç Hotel

The business model of Artıç Hotel is examined in detail up to this part. The critical part of the study is about finding the answers to the question of “how to innovate the business model”. It is beneficial to give a definition about business model and business model innovation here. While business model is about how to do business, business model innovation is about how to do business in new/better ways. Here is the figure of business model. Business model innovation can also be defined as the process of value creation while changing the current business model or adapting an innovative approach. In other words, any positive change in a business model means business model innovation.

Most of the tourists who stayed at Artıç Hotel are domestic tourists. In the previous sections, there is an analysis of these tourists based on the duration of

accommodation. Whether it is one night, two nights or more, most of the tourists are domestic tourists. So, it is determined as the most important segment.

Figure 6. Artıç Hotel Segment 1

Under domestic segment, Artıç Hotel should target Turkish families with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Artıç Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Artıç Hotel should mention these characteristics. These characteristics can be classified into three groups.

The first group mentions the importance of the **hotel's location and view**. Tourists can visit important historical and cultural places by walking.

- Best location for the historical and cultural places of Bursa
- Grand Mosque view from the rooms
- In the middle of old town
- Very close to all kinds of traditional food&beverages

The second group mentions the importance of **safety and trust in a hotel**. The hotel is operated by the founders for more than 50 years. The owners are from a well-known family in Bursa.

- Peaceful hotel for families
- An old family hotel

The third group is about the **price**. There are many competitors in the same location with the same characteristics. It is also a budget hotel.

- Budget hotel

The slogan: “feel the culture and history at the heart of old town of Bursa”

Artıç Hotel should target foreign tourists also. Foreign tourists market can be divided into three different sub-segments with the same value proposition (common point of these sub-segments are that they all consist of tourists who are curious about history and culture/cultural tourist). These sub-segments are Balkan countries (such as Bulgaria and Bosnia-Herzegovina), Middle-East countries (such as Saudi Arabia, Qatar and Kuwait) and Far-East countries (such as Indonesia and South Korea).

Figure 7. Artıç Hotel Segment 2

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Artıç Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-

segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Artıç Hotel should mention these characteristics. These characteristics can be classified into three groups.

The first group mentions the importance of the **hotel's location and view**. Tourists can visit important historical and cultural places by walking.

- Best location for the historical and cultural places of Bursa
- Grand Mosque view from the rooms
- In the middle of old town
- Very close to all kinds of traditional food&beverages

The second group mentions the importance of **safety and trust in a hotel**. The hotel is operated by the founders for more than 50 years. The owners are from a well-known family in Bursa.

- Peaceful hotel for families
- An old family hotel

The third group is about the **price**. There are many competitors in the same location with the same characteristics. It is also a budget hotel.

- Budget hotel

The slogan: "feel the culture and history at the heart of old town of Bursa"

3.3. General Evaluation of the First Round Implementation (3 Pilot Hotels)

Three hotels are selected for the pilot implementation. All of these hotels are located in Bursa. In spite of this, they all target different segments. Oksijen Zone Hotel is a winter hotel that is located at Uludağ region of Bursa. Although it is a winter hotel, the hotel owner wants the hotel to be open for 12 months. Gököz Natural Park is another hotel that is located at a town of Bursa in nature. Thus, its target segment is totally different from the previous one. The third hotel that has been selected is a city hotel named Artıç Hotel. Artıç Hotel is an old family hotel.

In the pilot round implementation stage, all of the business models of three hotels are examined with the tools and business models are innovated. According to the literature, a business model consists of four dimensions as mentioned before. If at least two of these dimensions are changed, it means that the business model has been innovated. In the table below, we can see a summary of the results.

Table 1. Changes in the Business Models for Pilot Implementation

Changes	Who (Target Customers / Segments)	What (Value proposition)	How (Value Chain)
Oksijen Zone	Yes	Yes	Partially
Gököz	Yes	Yes	Partially
Artıç	Yes	Yes	Partially

3.4. Second Round Implementation (5 Hotels + 2 Restaurants)

- Profiles of participating enterprises

There are five hotels in the second round of workshops. The first hotel is Bülbul Yuvası Butique Hotel. It is located in Foça, İzmir. The second hotel is Deniz Kabuğu Hotel that is located in Alaçatı, İzmir. Both of these hotels are located in İzmir but target totally different segments.

Third hotel of the second round implementation is Etenna Bungalow Hotel which is located in Çıralı, Antalya. It is a seaside hotel. The fourth hotel named Yonca Anjelika is located in Göcek, Muğla. Lastly, the fifth hotel named Park Mandalin is located at Şile, İstanbul.

One of the restaurants where the second round of implementation took place is Selçuk Restaurant, one of Bursa's long-established restaurants. The 10th application of the second round focused on a restaurant planned to be opened by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality in Cumalıkızık Village, which is on the UNESCO World Heritage List.

The characteristics of the second round hotels and restaurants are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the Hotels for Second Round

Name of the Hotel	Number of Employees	Location	Gender of the Owner
Bülbul Yuvası	7	Foça/İzmir	Male
Deniz Kabuğu	6	Alaçatı/İzmir	Female
Etenna Bungalow	8	Çıralı/Antalya	Female
Yonca Anjelika	7	Göcek/Muğla	Female
Park Mandalin	5	Şile/İstanbul	Female
Selçuk Restaurant	14	Osmangazi/Bursa	Male
Not yet confirmed (planned to be opened in Cumalıkızık Village by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality)	No employees yet	Yıldırım/Bursa	Male

- Design and implementation of business models

3.4.1. Blbl Yuvası Hotel

Blbl Yuvası Hotel is the fourth hotel that is been collaborated under the REMODEL Project. The aim of this study is to innovate the business model of Blbl Yuvası Hotel according to the BMI Lab methodology developed by BUU BMI Lab.

The address of Blbl Yuvası - Foa Boutique Hotel is “Atatrk Mah. 121. Sok. No: 20 Foa / İzmir”. In the “contact” section, detailed information regarding where the hotel is located, how to get there from different locations, and how long it takes to get there. In addition, Google Map information is given, which makes it easier to reach the hotel.

Reference: <https://www.bulbulyuvasi.com.tr/iletisim.php>

The business model of Blbl Yuvası Hotel is examined in detail up to this part. The critical part of the study is about finding the answers to the question of “how to innovate the business model”. It is beneficial to give a definition about business model and business model innovation here. While business model is about how to do business, business model innovation is about how to do business in new/better ways. Here is the

figure of business model. Business model innovation can also be defined as the process of value creation while changing the current business model or adapting an innovative approach. In other words, any positive change in a business model means business model innovation.

When it is looked at the current business model, the main problem is that Segmentation-Targeting-Positioning (STP) strategies of the hotel were not clear. Thus, a new segmentation study is conducted in order to understand the market. First, tourism market for Bülbül Yuvası Hotel is divided into two main segments that are called domestic tourist and foreign tourist segments.

STP strategies of Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should redesigned. It is located at the seaside and is open for 12 months. Thus, main segments should be winter and summer segments. Foça is one of the towns of İzmir. İzmir is visited by approximately 1700000 foreign tourists in 2024. Sub-segments should be both domestic and foreign tourists for winter and summer segments.

There were no available customer data about the customers of Bülbül Yuvası Hotel. As mentioned before, the first segment should be the “winter segment” for domestic and foreign tourists.

Figure 8. Bülbül Yuvası Hotel Segment 1

Under winter segment, Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should target “couples” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should mention these characteristics. These characteristics can be classified into three groups.

The first group mentions the importance of the **hotel’s location and view**. Tourists can feel the romantic and inspiring view. In addition, they can go for a walk to Foça old town.

- Romantic sea view
- Inspiring view
- Close to Foça old town

The second group mentions the importance of **inspiring design of the hotel**. The interior design of the hotel is inspiring.

- Design of the rooms
- Inspiring interior design

The third group mentions the importance of **rich breakfast with local food served at the hotel**. The breakfast is open buffet.

There were no available customer data about the customers of Bülbül Yuvası Hotel. As mentioned before, the second segment should be the “summer segment” for domestic and foreign tourists.

Figure 9. Bülbül Yuvası Hotel Segment 2

Under summer segment, Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should target “couples” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Bülbül Yuvası Hotel should mention these characteristics. These characteristics can be classified into two groups.

The first group mentions the importance of the **hotel's location and view**. Tourists can feel the romantic and inspiring view. In addition, they can go for a walk to Foça old town.

- Magnificent sea
- Walking distance to the beach
- Romantic sea view
- Inspiring view
- Close to Foça old town

The second group mentions the importance of **inspiring design of the hotel**. The interior design of the hotel is inspiring.

- Design of the rooms
- Inspiring interior design

The third group mentions the importance of **rich breakfast with local food served at the hotel**. The breakfast is open buffet.

3.4.2. Deniz Kabuğu Hotel

The address of Deniz Kabuğu Hotel is “Alaçatı, 12080 Sok No:6, 35930 Çeşme/İzmir”. In the “contact” section, google map location of the hotel is provided which makes it easier to reach the hotel. Also, phone and e-mail information is provided.

<https://denizkabuguhotel.com/en/contact/>

The hotel's location is mentioned, but there is no information about the distance to important places and public transportation options.

STP strategies of Deniz Kabağu Hotel should be redesigned. It is located far from the seaside, but there is opportunity to swim in Alaçatı. The hotel has a big garden where you can relax, eat, drink or read something. The hotel is in a silent location. In spite of this, it is 15 minutes walk to the center of Alaçatı. The hotel is open from April to December. **High season is summer season** but **May, September and October** are also busy. The hotel should focus on the months from May to October. That is totally 6 months.

Although the hotel welcomes families with children, we think that it should not be the main target. When the customer database of 2024 is analysed, it can be seen that **68% of the customers are couples without children**. 6.5% of the customers are solo-travelers. The rest of the customers are families with children. The target segment should be couples firstly. When the ages of the customers are analysed, it is seen that approximately 55% of the customers are between 30 and 50. In addition, because of

the Alaçatı destination's characteristics the hotel should adopt **“adult-only concept”** (+12).

So, it is not reasonable to focus on couples and solo-travelers. The board type of the hotel is **“bed and breakfast”**. Some important amenities of the hotel are listed as follows.

- Restaurant and bar
- Big garden
- Quality booklets
- Turkish breakfast

There also some activities that the tourist can carry out in Alaçatı.

- Night life, live music
- All kinds of bars and restaurants
- Go swimming by car or boat or by tour to bays and islands.
- Visiting Çeşme and historical places
- Daily tours to Ephesus

We analysed the location, characteristics of the hotel and the environment. In addition to these, we conducted interviews with the hotel manager and did workshops with the hotel employees. Finally, target segment is defined for the hotel. As seen from the analysis results, target segment should be domestic but the same selling proposition can also target foreign tourists with the same characteristics.

Target segment should have these characteristics.

- Domestic/Foreign tourists

- Middle and upper-middle income group
- 30-50 years-old
- Well-educated
- White-collar employees
- Calmness seekers during day
- Couples and solo travelers
- Sea lovers
- History lovers

According to the analysis of customer database, Deniz Kabuğu Hotel should target this segment below.

Figure 10. Deniz Kabuğu Hotel Segment 1

Deniz Kabuğu Hotel should target “couples-solo travelers” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Deniz Kabuğu Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Deniz Kabuğu Hotel should mention these characteristics for couples and solo-travelers.

- Isolated and calm hotel
- Close to some historical places (Çeşme Castle, churches)
- Close to old town of Alaçatı
- Close to Ephesus (daily tours)
- Magnificent sea (especially boat tours to bays and near islands)
- Quality and rich breakfast
- Free tea and cookies for the hotel customers in the afternoon.
- Best hotel for couples and solo-travelers
- Close to local bazaars

3.4.3. Etenna Bungalow Hotel

The address of Etenna Beach Bungalows is “Ulupınar mah. Çıralı Sok.Kemer / Antalya”. In the “contact” section, google map location of the hotel is provided which makes it easier to reach the hotel. Also, phone and e-mail information is provided.

<https://www.etennaholiday.com/en/contact-us/>

The hotel's location is given, but there is no information about the distance from the city center, to important places and whether there are public transportation options or not.

When it is looked at the current business model, the main problem is that the hotel has not defined target segments. In addition, because there aren't any specified target segments, there aren't any positioning strategies for these segments.

STP strategies of Etenna Bungalow Hotel should redesigned. It is located at the seaside and is open for summer season between April and October. Çıralı is located at an isolated seaside of beautiful south coast of Antalya, Türkiye.

We analysed the location, characteristics of the hotel and the environment. In addition to these, we conducted interviews with the hotel manager and did workshops with the hotel employees. Finally, two segments are defined for the hotel.

- Domestic/foreign families (nature and sea lovers, sun seekers, peaceful and calm beach holiday)

- Domestic/foreign couples (couples seeking romance and calmness in nature by the sea)

Slogan: a calm and peaceful place between green and blue...

There were no available customer data about the customers of Etenna Bungalow Hotel. As mentioned before, the first segment should be the “domestic/foreign families”.

Figure 11. Etenna Bungalow Hotel Segment 1

Etenna Bungalow Hotel should target “families” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Etenna Bungalow Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Etenna Bungalow Hotel should mention these characteristics. These characteristics can be classified into two groups.

- Domestic/foreign families (nature and sea lovers, sun seekers, peaceful and calm beach holiday)

The first group mentions the importance of the **hotel's natural environment**. Tourists can feel the nature view. In addition, they can ride a bike and go for a walk in nature.

- Nature, sea and sun
- Best place for biking and walking

The second group mentions the **characteristics of the location of the hotel**. The interior design of the rooms is also inspiring. The hotel rooms are separately designed in a big green garden. There are various trees and plants in the garden. The garden is in an isolated area where the kids can play and walk by themselves.

- Peacefulness and calmness
- Isolated and safe place for children

There were no available customer data about the customers of Etenna Bungalow Hotel. As mentioned before, the second segment should be the “domestic/foreign couples”.

Figure 12. Etenna Bungalow Hotel Segment 2

Etenna Bungalow Hotel should also target “couples” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Etenna Bungalow Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Etenna Bungalow Hotel should mention these characteristics. These characteristics can be classified into two groups.

- Domestic/foreign couples (couples seeking romance and calmness in nature by the sea)

The first group mentions the importance of the **hotel's romantic view**. The hotel rooms are separately designed in a big green garden. Every room has a table in the front. So, tourists can spend time alone with themselves. In addition, the hotel has a restaurant with a magnificent sea view. They can also use the restaurant for romantic purposes. Tourists can watch the the nature and sea view during day and night.

- Romantic day and night view

The second group mentions the **characteristics of the location/environment of the hotel**.

- Peacefulness and calmness
- Nature, sea and sun
- Isolated place

3.4.4. Yonca Anjelika Hotel

The address of Yonca Anjelika Hotel is "Göcek Mahallesi Gonca Sokak No: 10 Fethiye, Muğla, Türkiye". In the "contact" section, google map location of the hotel is provided which makes it easier to reach the hotel. Also, phone and e-mail information is

provided. In addition, they added a “get in touch” section in which they help to solve the problem and ensure satisfaction.

<https://www.yoncaanjelikahotel.com/en/contact/>

The hotel's location is given, but there is no information about the distance from the city center, to important places and whether there are public transportation options or not.

Although it is not located far from the seaside, there is no opportunity to swim in the center of Göcek. In spite of this, the hotel has a mini pool. The hotel is open for 12 months but it will be reasonable to focus on spring and summer season (March-October) more. It makes 8 months in a year. The hotel has an “**adult-only concept**”. So, it is not reasonable to focus on families. The board type of the hotel is “**bed and breakfast**”. Some important amenities of the hotel are listed as follows:

- Bar/restaurant
- Mini pool
- Quality booklets
- Turkish breakfast
- Yoga sessions

- Music nights

There also some activities that the tourist can carry out in Göcek.

- Joining a boat tour
- Walking in nature
- Go swimming by car or boat
- Visiting cultural and historical places (For instance, ancient cities)

We analysed the location, characteristics of the hotel and the environment. In addition to these, we conducted interviews with the hotel manager and did workshops with the hotel employees. Finally, target segment is defined for the hotel.

Target segment should have these characteristics.

- Middle and upper-middle income group
- Over 35 years-old
- Well-educated
- White-collar employees
- Nature and history lovers
- Couples and solo travelers
- Sea lovers

There were no available customer data about the customers of Yonca Anjelika Hotel.

As mentioned before, the segment should be as follows.

Figure 13. Yonca Anjelika Hotel Segment 1

Yonca Anjelika Hotel should target “couples-solo travelers” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section.

Positioning strategy is about the delivery of value proposition to the target segment/s. Yonca Anjelika Hotel should have a main positioning strategy and adapt it according to the sub-segment characteristics. Generally, positioning strategy of Yonca Anjelika Hotel should mention these characteristics for couples and solo-travelers.

- Natural and historical place
- Close to ancient cities
- Best place for walking in nature
- Magnificent sea (especially boat tours to bays and near islands)
- Isolated and calm hotel

- Quality and rich breakfast
- Mini pool

Slogan: Visit Göcek where nature, sea and history meet.

3.4.5. Park Mandalin Hotel

The last hotel whose business model was studied under the REMODEL Project is Park Mandalin located in Ağva Region. Ağva is a coastal village in Istanbul's Şile district, set between two rivers (Göksu and Yeşilçay) flowing into the Black Sea. It's known for riverside boutique hotels/bungalows, scenic coves (Kilimli & Kadirga) and easy weekender access from Istanbul.

Ağva first gained widespread recognition in the early 2000s through scenes featured in the TV series "Bir İstanbul Masalı", which positioned the area as a romantic weekend destination. In the following years, other productions such as "Unutulmaz", "No:309", and "Erkenci Kuş" further enhanced its appeal, reinforcing Ağva's image as a popular escape for domestic tourists. However, the COVID-19 pandemic brought a period of stagnation, with tourism activity temporarily declining. Today, increasing competition, the rise of alternative destinations, and decreasing demand make it difficult for Ağva to maintain its former level of attractiveness.

Park Mandalin Hotel is located in a calm and peaceful area surrounded by nature and offering a relaxing atmosphere. The hotel located by the Ağva /Göksu river where guests can enjoy breakfast, spend time reading, or simply rest in a serene environment. Although it is in a tranquil location, it is still close to the region's cultural and natural attractions. **Kadirga Bay and Gelin Kayası** is accessible mainly by boat tours, these bays is famous for its rock formations and dramatic cliffs—perfect for

photography and nature lovers. **Yeşilçay Stream** is another popular waterway, offering lively scenery and walking paths and fresh fish in the nearby local restaurants. **Ağva Beach** is a long sandy coastline with clean waters, ideal for swimming and sunbathing, especially during summer. There are also hidden waterfalls (**Hacıllı Waterfalls & Caves**) in the forest, these waterfalls and caves are ideal for hiking and exploring nature.

The hotel operates throughout the year (12 month), but the high season is during summer months. Additionally, May, September, and October are also active thanks to the mild climate and tourism potential of the region. Therefore, the hotel should particularly focus on the 6-month period between May and October.

According to information from interviews and WS, it is observed that 95% of guests are domestic tourists mainly from Istanbul, Ankara, Bursa and Eskişehir, while 5 % are foreigners mainly from Russia, Dubai, Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Kuwait and Qatar. Apart from them, Northern Europe, Italy and Spain. 50-60% of the customers aged between 30-45. The dominant segment includes middle-income and upper-middle-income groups, particularly white-collar professionals, retired people, and academics. Solo travelers are relatively fewer, and families with children are out of scope because it is an adults-only hotel (+15) . Therefore, the hotel should position itself mainly for couples and middle-aged visitors who appreciate calmness, confidentiality, and sincerity.

The board type of the hotel is “bed and breakfast”. Some important amenities of the hotel are listed as follows.

- Clean and comfortable room
- Restaurant and bar (High quality food and drinks)
- Turkish breakfast

- Riverside garden
- Calm environment

In addition to hotel facilities, visitors can engage in several activities around the region:

- Visiting natural attractions (Kadırga Bay and Gelin, Yeşilçay Stream, Hacılı Waterfalls & Caves)
- Boat Tours on Göksu and Yeşilçay Rivers
- Beach and Swimming
- Nature Walks and Hiking
- Experiencing local gastronomy– tasting fresh fish

As seen from the analysis results, target segment should be domestic but the same selling proposition can also target foreign tourists with the same characteristics.

Target segment should have these characteristics.

- Mainly domestic, but also foreign tourists with similar traits
- Middle and upper-middle-income groups
- 30–64 years old
- Well-educated (white-collar, retired, academics)
- Couples and calmness seekers
- Travelers who value sincerity and confidentiality
- Tourists interested in gastronomy, local culture, and peaceful stays
- Nature lovers

According to the analysis of customer database, Park Mandalin should target this segment below.

Figure 14. Park Mandalin Hotel Segment 1

Park Mandalin should target “couples-solo travelers” with a value proposition mentioned under positioning section. In addition, considering the potential offered by the location and natural attractions, besides the current visitor profile, there appears to be a potential but not yet active sub-segment 2 consisting of young people, groups or couples who are interested in outdoor sports. However, in order for this segment to be activated, hotels and the local municipality need to act together and develop a positioning and marketing strategy for the destination. For example, activities such as canoe races, outdoor sports events, or festivals could be organized.

A positioning strategy defines how the hotel conveys its value proposition to its chosen target groups. Hotel Park Mandalin should determine a central positioning platform and

make modifications based on sub-segment profiles. When addressing couples and solo travelers, the strategy should particularly underline the following aspects.

- Isolated and calm hotel
- Romantic atmosphere
- Quality foods and rich breakfast
- Magnificent river view
- Close to beach and bay
- Close to natural attractions
- Boat activities / Hiking
- Best hotel for couples and solo-travelers

3.4.6. Selçuk Restaurant

Selçuk Restaurant is located in the Osmangazi district of Bursa, within the Reşat Oyal Cultural Park. The park was opened in 1955 by Reşat Oyal, Mayor of Bursa, under the name 'Kültürpark'. Situated in the centre of Bursa, the park covers an area of 393,000 square metres. The park, which features a lake area where visitors can ride pedal boats, tea gardens, restaurants, the Bursa Archaeology Museum, and an open-air theatre, is of great importance to the city centre due to its location, size, and greenery. Recently, concerts organised by the Bursa Metropolitan Municipality and held in the open-air theatre within Kültürpark have led to an increase in visitor demand for the park. These features make the park an attraction for both the people of Bursa and local and foreign tourists. The park provides an appealing environment, especially for families with children, while also offering fun activities such as pedal boating.

Selçuk Restaurant has been serving in Kültürpark since 1967. Now run by the second generation, the restaurant continues its operations with a total of 14 employees. The venue has a covered area of 360 square metres and an open area of 293 square metres, with a total capacity of 100 people. Selçuk Restaurant mainly welcomes its guests in its garden during the summer, and the covered area is not used. Surrounded by plane and maple trees, the garden offers a peaceful atmosphere immersed in nature for those seeking to escape the hustle and bustle of city life. The menu, which reinterprets traditional Turkish cuisine with a modern twist, varies according to the season but always preserves the flavours that regulars are accustomed to and seek. The restaurant owner, Mr Selçuk, visits each table to listen to his guests' experiences and exemplifies sincere hospitality. The indoor section, which is open on rainy spring days and during the winter, has attracted attention since the restaurant's establishment in 1967 with its original wooden ceiling and nostalgic atmosphere.

This carefully preserved area reflects the restaurant's deep-rooted identity with its well-maintained structure and the spirit it carries from the past to the present. Approximately 5% of the restaurant's visitors are foreign, while 20% are local tourists.

The restaurant does not have a website. Its social media channels are limited to an Instagram account, which is managed by the owner but does not feature regular content sharing. Furthermore, the Instagram account does not include any information about the restaurant's location. The service processes observed in the restaurant and dining areas are generally carried out using traditional methods. Order taking, service delivery, and payment transactions are carried out manually, which causes slowdowns during busy times.

Interviews, field observations and analysis of customer comments reveal that Selçuk Restaurant's customer profile consists mainly of local visitors. Customers are middle-aged and older individuals living in Bursa, as well as domestic tourists visiting from outside the city. Although the proportion of foreign tourists is limited, tourists visiting Kültürpark have the potential to visit the restaurant. The opportunities offered by Kültürpark for children and family activities make Selçuk Restaurant a preferred venue for families with children. Selçuk Restaurant's long-standing history positions it not only as a place to eat and drink, but also as a venue where memories are refreshed and nostalgic bonds are formed.

Selçuk Restaurant's core value proposition includes the following elements.

- Established and nostalgic restaurant identity (characteristic of being a place of memories)
- Authentic Turkish cuisine experience with local and seasonal products
- Hygiene and food safety (open kitchen, ISO 22000, transparent kitchen processes)
- Experience-focused service: gastronomy workshops, wine tastings, event menus
- Digital conveniences: QR menu, online reservations, mobile payment
- Family-friendly environment: non-smoking environment, children's menu
- Loyalty and belonging: long-standing customer relationships, opportunity to refresh memories

By realising Selçuk Restaurant's value proposition, the products and services it can use to reach its target customer segment are as follows:

- Healthy, sustainable and seasonal food and beverage options
- Gluten-free, vegan and vegetarian menu alternatives

- Open kitchen experience and transparency in the production process
- Digital reservations, QR code menus and contactless payment services
- Kitchen and service that comply with hygiene standards and are regularly inspected
- Events and workshops (cooking classes, tasting days)
- Gift product sales (special sauces, homemade products)
- Services supported by visibility on social media and digital platforms
- A menu highlighting Bursa cuisine (gastronomic identity)

3.4.7. The restaurant planned to be opened in Cumalıkızık Village by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality

Located in the Yıldırım district of Bursa and listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, Cumalıkızık Village is an important cultural destination for both local and foreign tourists, thanks to its unique residential architecture reflecting Ottoman civil architecture, narrow stone streets, rural lifestyle culture, and gastronomic heritage.

Thanks to its proximity to the city centre of Bursa and its historical identity, Cumalıkızık experiences a heavy influx of visitors, especially on weekends and during the tourist season. Cumalıkızık Village stands out not only for its architectural heritage but also for its traditional production methods, local culinary culture, and social practices unique to village life.

The breakfast houses and home-made product sales that have been operating in the village for many years form the basis of the region's gastronomy-based visitor experience. However, the fact that this structure is largely fragmented, has varying

standards, and is fragile in terms of sustainability has necessitated the development of a comprehensive and exemplary business model led by the municipality.

In this context, the Cumalıkızık Municipal Restaurant has been designed as a strategic initiative aimed at both preserving cultural heritage and supporting local development. The planned restaurant is designed to operate year-round. An architectural approach harmonious with nature and the historical environment is considered one of the fundamental components of the restaurant experience.

The restaurant is intended to be operated with a spatial understanding that does not harm the traditional fabric of the village, but rather makes this fabric visible and transforms it into an experience. The restaurant has the potential to be more than just a 'place to eat' for visitors; it is intended to be a meeting point where the story of Cumalıkızık can be experienced.

The core value proposition offered by the Cumalıkızık Municipal Restaurant is shaped around the following elements:

- Local and fine-dining elements and evening meals
- Experiences suited to local, cultural, special workshops and events
- Quality, appropriate service
- Children's activity areas
- Social media corner
- Parking and Melex transport to the restaurant for physically disabled and families with babies
- Raspberry-themed food and beverages
- Open kitchen

The products and services that will support the implementation of this value proposition can be summarised as follows:

- Menu structure based on local and geographically marked products
- Seasonal, healthy and sustainable food and beverage options
- Vegan, vegetarian and special dietary alternatives
- Open kitchen and production processes visible to visitors
- Gastronomy and cultural heritage-themed workshops and events
- Local gift products (jams, sauces, dried products, etc.)
- Visitor experience supported by digital information and guidance systems
- Modern and healthy presentation of local flavours (fine dining, allergen/vegan menu)
- Family-friendly and accessible environment (children's area, prayer room, car park)
- Social media and cultural experience area (photo corner, influencer visits, workshops)
- Quality service and digital conveniences (English-speaking staff, digital menu, cleanliness, feedback)

4. Impact Assessment

4.1. Assessment Methodology

"Given the limited time between implementation and reporting, a short-term impact assessment strategy was adopted, combining micro KPI tracking, and brief interviews. This rapid assessment approach allows for early insight into model applicability and initial outcomes, while setting a basis for future evaluation."

Short-Term and Practical Impact Assessment Strategy (2-Stage Approach)

Given the current conditions of the REMODEL:

- Business models are still in the early implementation phase
- Time is limited (D4.3 must be completed by December 2025)
- Long-term impact observation is not yet feasible

The most realistic and efficient way forward is to conduct a short-term but meaningful impact assessment. Below is a practical, quick-to-implement 2-step model for collecting data and evaluating early results:

Measurable Early Indicators – Micro KPI Set

Identify basic indicators that can be tracked even during early stages of implementation:

- Changes in the design of the channels used for reaching customers
 - Web site
 - Social media
 - Customer review management

- Activities for new segments (new value creation for new segments)

Goal: Quantify early effects of the model with light data collection.

Semi-Structured Interviews

Conducting short (15-minute) interviews with SMEs.

Possible guiding questions:

1. What do you think of the business model presented? Could you give a general assessment?
2. Do you think the business model presented will benefit your hotel?
3. Do you think the presented business model is realizable/applicable for your hotel?
4. Do you think the business model presented will make your hotel more profitable and competitive?
5. Which of the suggestions within the presented business model do you think are faster and easier to implement?
6. What challenges might you encounter in implementing the presented business model? (Personnel, budget, technology, infrastructure, etc.)
7. Do you think the business model presented is sustainable for your hotel?

Goal: Enrich the survey findings with qualitative insight and direct quotes.

4.2. Early Performance Indicators

Following studies conducted by BMI Lab, Business Models were presented to hotels. Actions and recommendations that hotels could implement based on these Business Models were presented. Various indicators were analyzed using secondary data to

measure the impact of the Business Models presented. Changes and activities implemented by hotels regarding these actions and recommendations were identified through analysis of their websites and social media accounts. The impact of these changes and activities on customers was analyzed through Google reviews.

-Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa

The Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa's website (<https://www.oksijenzone.com/>) has been reviewed and it has been determined that the following recommended actions and activities have been implemented.

- It was determined that the number of customer-friendly statements on the website pages has increased.
- Deficiencies in restaurant operating hours, food and beverage offerings, service features, etc. have been addressed (Figure 15).
- Entertainment and event content proposed within the Business Model has been added to the website (Figure 16).
- It was determined that social media links that were previously inaccessible on the website have been activated.
- It has been added to the website regarding campaigns and discounts (Figure17).

Figure 15. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Restaurant Information

Figure 16. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Entertainment and Event Information

Figure 17. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Campaign and Discount Information

Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa's Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/oksijenzonehotelsuludag/>) has been reviewed and it has been determined that the following recommended actions and activities have been implemented.

- It has been determined that income-generating activities other than accommodation and restaurants have been diversified through workshops (Figure 18).
- The targeted customer segment was attracted to the hotel through music and entertainment themed events (Figure 19).
- Offers have been prepared for the business world for periods when occupancy rates are lower (Figure 20).
- In order to extend the ski season and increase occupancy rates, price, promotion and camp-based campaigns have been created.
- Iftar menus and whirling dervish shows have been prepared to alleviate the effects of Ramadan (Figure 21).

- The stagnation experienced within the hotel due to the lack of skiing in the evenings is eliminated with ceramics and painting workshops in which adults and children can participate (Figure 22).

When Google reviews of Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa were examined, it was determined that the comments were not moderated and that no response was given to positive or negative comments.

Figure 18. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Workshops

Figure 19. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Music Events

Figure 20. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Campaigns & Offers

Figure 21. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Ramadan Iftars

Figure 22. Oksijen Zone Hotel & Spa-Evening Workshops

-Artıç Hotel

When Artıç Hotel's website (<https://www.artichotel.com/>) was examined, it was determined that there was no change in the implementation of the Business Model actions and suggestions.

Artıç Hotel's Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/artichotel/>) has been reviewed and it has been determined that the following recommended actions and activities have been implemented.

- In order to increase income-generating activities other than accommodation, iftar dinners were organized during Ramadan (Figure 23).
- The hotel's 3 halls are now open for engagements, weddings and other ceremonies (Figure 24).
- The hotel hosted meeting organizations organized by the business world (Figure 25).
- The hotel's income-generating activities have been enriched with various cultural and artistic events and educational organizations (Figure 26).
- Handicraft workshops have begun to be held at the hotel (Figure 27).

When Google reviews of Artıç Hotel were examined, it was determined that the negative comments were responded to, and the responses given were not in a way that would compensate for the service error.

Figure 23. Artıç Hotel-Ramadan Iftars

Figure 24. Artıç Hotel-Wedding Organizations

Figure 25. Artıç Hotel-Meeting Organizations

Figure 26. Artıç Hotel-Events

Figure 27. Artıç Hotel-Workshops

-Deniz Kabuğu Hotel

When Deniz Kabuğu Hotel's website (<https://denizkabuguhotel.com/>) was examined, it was determined that there was no change in the implementation of the Business Model actions and suggestions.

Deniz Kabuğu Hotel's Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/denizkabuguhotel/>) has been reviewed and it has been determined that the following recommended actions and activities have been implemented.

- Activities carried out by the hotel on a daily basis to improve the quality of service were shared (Figure 28).
- Collaborations were made with social media influencers, and discount campaigns were organized during periods of low demand (Figure 29).
- Positive comments from customers based on their experiences at the hotel were shared as social media posts (Figure 30).
- The hotel acts like a local guide to customers visiting Çeşme and Alaçatı, guiding them on activities, food and drink, etc (Figure 31).

When the Google reviews of Deniz Kabuğu Hotel were examined, it was determined that the comments were managed, that there were no low-rated comments after the BMI Lab team's visit, and that high-rated comments were thanked.

Figure 28. Deniz Kabuğu Hotel-Value-Adding Services

denizkabughotel Alaçatı, Çeşme

15% OFF

denizkabughotel Fransız balkonlu ve design odalarımızda küçük bir sürpriz
Bu hafta sonu Alaçatı'ya kaçmak isteyenlere minik bir indirim bıraktık.

Bu videoda

Muhammet Uzun [Takip Et](#)

Figure 29. Deniz Kabuğu Hotel-Campaigns and Collaborations

Figure 30. Deniz Kabuğu Hotel-Comment Sharing

denizkabuguhotel ✓
Denizkabağı Hotel Alaçatı

**Çeşme'de Gün Batımı
Nereden İzlenir?**

Lezzet ve Manzaranın Buluştuğı
4 Harika Durak!

denizkabuguhotel ✓
Global Genius • Swing String Fling (feat. Davi...

**Sokaktan
Gelen Tatlar:
Alaçatı'da Ne
Yenir?**

55 2 25

denizkabuguhotel Çeşme'de Gün Batımı Nereden İzlenir?
Akşam yemeğı eşliğinde unutulmaz manzaralar...🌅🇵🇹. 1.

81 12

mehlika.sarac ve diğer kişiler beğendi

denizkabuguhotel Alaçatı'da 4 durak, 4 lezzet! 💜🍷

1. **Eli Yeme İçme** 🍷 Asya mutfağının Alaçatı yorumu. İtirli margaritası 🍷 favorimizdi! @eliyemeicme
2. **Roka Bahçe** 🌿 Ferah bahçesi ve 🍷 deniz ürünlü paellasıyla çok keyifli. @rokaabahce
3. **Arpege Pastane** 💜🍷 Ekler & lavantalı dondurma ile tatlı bir mola! @arpegepatisserie
4. **Tius Bar** 🍷 Yıldızburnu'nda gün batımı + kokteyl = yazın özeti. @tius.bar

Favorin hangisi? 📄 Kaydet, 💬 yorum yap, ✉ etiketle!alaçatı2025 #alaçatirehberi #alaçatilezzetleri #alaçatimekanları #çeşme #çeşme2025 #çeşmehaberleri #egelezzetleri #egeakşamı #rakıbalı #balıkrestoranı #alaçatıakşamı #alaçatigezisi #gurmelokasyonlar #mekanönerisi #yemekturizmi #yemeicme #noodlelover #paellalovers #lavantalıdondurma #arpegepastane #eliyemeicme #rokaabahce #tiusbar #sunsetcocktails #foodieplaces #instagramturkey #gezginyorumlar #keşfet

30 Mayıs • EFEKT İLE YAPILDI

31 10

denizkabuguhotel Sıcacık sokaklardan, buz gibi sahillere... Hadi birlikte tadına bakalım! 🍷🍷🍷🍷🍷

15 10

denizkabuguhotel 📍 Haziran'da Çeşme'deyiz! Dans, tarih, deniz ve akıl oyunları... İşte ayın öne çıkan etkinlikleri! 🎵🌿🍷

- 🌟 6 Haziran – Mind Against @sommerklein
- 🌟 14 Haziran – Monolink @yuzubeach
- 🌟 12/14/19/21/26 Haziran – Gece Gece Efes Turları @visiturla
- 🌟 23-29 Haziran – Uluslararası Açık Satranç Turnuvası @cesmebld

Bu gönderiyi kaydet 📄 @denizkabuguhotel Her hafta yenisi gelecek. Yorumlara favorini bırak! 🍷 #beachparty #djlife #travelgram #festivalvibes #cesmeetkinlikleri #cesmegecehayati #turkeyevents #mindagainst #monolinklive #sommerklein #yuzubeach #visiturla #efesturu #cesmesatrancturnuvasi #alaçatı #çeşme #travelnow #holidayspirit #egeakdeniz #egegecehayati #egeetkinlik #enjoyeverymoment #keşfet

2 Haziran

Figure 31. Deniz Kabağı Hotel-Guidance Service to Customers

-Yonca Anjelika Hotel

Yonca Anjelika Hotel website (<https://www.yoncaanjelikahotel.com/>) has been reviewed and it has been determined that the following recommended actions and activities have been implemented.

- The activities menu has been added and the activities held at the hotel have been posted on the website (Figure 32).
- Deficiencies in the services menu have been corrected and the services offered have been fully added to the site (Figure 33).

Figure 32. Yonca Anjelika Hotel-Activities

Figure 33. Yonca Anjelika Hotel-Services

Yonca Anjelika Hotel's Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/yoncaanjelika/>) has been reviewed and it has been determined that the following recommended actions and activities have been implemented.

- The hotel has created a beverage and cocktail menu to increase its revenue-generating activities (Figure 34).
- The hotel's founding story was shared, aiming to connect customers with the hotel and strengthen the relationship (Figure 35).
- Dinner and yoga events were held and the hotel's income-generating activities were aimed to increase (Figure 35).
- With the French Night event, events that are suitable for and attract attention of the customer segment have begun to be held (Figure 36).

When the Google reviews of Yonca Anjelika Hotel were examined, it was determined that the comments were managed, that there were no low-rated comments after the BMI Lab team's visit, and that high-rated comments were thanked.

Figure 34. Yonca Anjelika Hotel-Beverage Menu

Figure 35. Yonca Anjelika Hotel-The Story of the Hotel and Events

Figure 36. Yonca Anjelika Hotel-French Night

- Selçuk Restaurant

Selçuk Restaurant does not have a website. On Selçuk Restaurant's Instagram account:

- More frequent posts have begun
- Visits to the restaurant by famous guests have begun to be shared via the Instagram account
- Posts about the items on the menu and wine tasting events have begun

In addition, Selçuk Restaurant has started to respond promptly to all positive and negative comments made by customers on the Google platform. The restaurant's Google platform rating rose from 4.2 to 4.3 before the innovative SM model establishment efforts began.

- The restaurant planned to be opened in Cumalıkızık Village by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality

As the restaurant has not yet opened, it has not been possible to obtain early indicators.

4.3. Insights from Semi-Structured Interviews

The semi-structured interview consists of seven questions that explains the impact of business model from the perspective of hotel owners. 7 hotel and 1 restaurant owners accepted to participate in the interview. As the restaurant planned to be established by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality in Cumalıkızık is still in the process of being established, it has not been possible to receive feedback on the innovative business

model. Key themes from the interviews and quotes from hotel owners are shown under each question below.

Q1: What do you think of the business model presented? Could you give a general assessment?

*I totally agree with the model. Some of the points you mentioned is actually we aware of, but generally overlook. Therefore, highlighting these points is an **important factor** for us (Oksijen Zone Hotel).*

*I fully agree with the points raised in the model. Many of these are issues that we already feel and are aware of, but we have been rather slow in taking action. In this sense, the business model is also a motivating factor for us. What we especially need now are **practical suggestions** on which methods would be most appropriate to use and how to put them into practice. For example, we would appreciate guidance on how to emphasize our key value propositions and how to clearly communicate the difference between day-trip visits and overnight stays in our marketing and communication activities (Gököz Natural Park).*

*First of all, let me say this: we've seen that things we used to consider trivial are actually important. The website is a particularly compelling example. We've become increasingly aware of the importance of social media tools (especially simultaneous use) within the business model. We've observed that our hotel is primarily occupied by couples. I believe we should also **target families with children** (Artıç Hotel).*

*We were already accomplishing some things. But it turned out to be quite good and productive for us. We realized **we had overlooked things we hadn't really cared about before**. It was nice to see these things (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel).*

*It was especially great for us to **see things through the eyes of academics** who are involved in this field. At the same time, having the other group come, stay, and evaluate the hotel from the perspective of potential customers was also beneficial for us. The evaluations made particularly for the rooms and the restaurant were very useful. Since we are sometimes inside the operation, we may not notice certain things or think about them in such detail. Even though we have a large team working in the background, we still may not be able to see everything. Therefore, having educators who are actively involved in the field assess these aspects—both at that time and now—has been **very valuable** to us (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).*

*I think it created a very strong awareness. To be honest, it came at a time when I was very ready for this and really wanted it. It was a very good journey for us, and you guided us through it very well. Let me add something here as well. I think that **even very experienced professionals in tourism should go through this kind of work in order to overcome their professional blind spots** (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).*

*The proposed business model is highly useful. Following the face-to-face meeting, the owner displayed both the Business Model Canvas and the Value Proposition Canvas in a visible area for all staff. **The model is easy to comprehend, and the recommendations provided are clear, focused, and actionable** (Park Mandalin Hotel).*

*First of all, thank you very much for choosing us for this project. I can see that it is a very valuable project. Well done. We believe that there are areas here where **we can benefit greatly**. (Selçuk Restaurant)*

Q2: Do you think the business model presented will benefit your hotel/restaurant?

Of course. Especially, we are a hotel open 12 months but unable to attract customers all the time (Oksijen Zone Hotel).

Definitely (Gököz Natural Park)

I think it is definitely **useful** (Artıç Hotel).

Actually, the biggest benefit was **refocusing on the customer and taking a fresh look at ourselves**. When you focus on good service, you don't need to do anything else (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel).

Yes, I definitely agree. We were actually aware that we were lacking especially in the parts related to the website. I can say that this section was somewhat overlooked from our side. Focusing on this area is important because, as you know, everything now operates through websites and social media platforms. In the past, referrals carried more weight. My husband has been a business owner for 18–19 years. Previously, aside from social media platforms, business was conducted mostly through referrals. But now these online channels have become extremely important. That's why I honestly think it will be very effective (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).

Of course, our perspective has changed. We were able to test and confirm that we were on the right track in the things we already knew. And it also changed our perspective on certain points. In that sense, it was very beneficial for us (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).

Definitely. But under some constraints (Park Mandalin Hotel).

Definitely. (Selçuk Restaurant)

Q3. Do you think the presented business model is realizable/applicable for your hotel?

*These recommendations are **realizable but under some constraints**. Due to our location, sometimes are unable to find qualified or technical personnel (Oksijen Zone Hotel).*

*Each of the recommendations is **realizable** (Gököz Natural Park).*

***Yes, I do.** I think we need to develop a strategy specifically for the domestic and international segments served by the business model (Artıç Hotel).*

I think the things we discussed could have been implemented, but sometimes unexpected things happen. For example, the rock festival was canceled this year. We had done a lot of preparation for this event (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel).

*Yes, I think **it is feasible** because we already have a team working on these areas. Once I share your suggestions with them, I believe what you mentioned can be resolved in a short time. I think the same not only for the website but also for all the recommendations and suggestions you provided (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).*

*You know this whole pricing issue... I'm really tired of the pressure coming from around us and from the situation in Göcek. But despite all that, **thanks to you, we were able to resist** (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).*

*Even if not all of them are applicable due to budget and infrastructure constraints, **many of them are applicable** (Park Mandalin Hotel).*

***I think it's feasible. Yes.** I'm just not sure about the open kitchen. It's not really possible to have an environment where all the cooking is done outside, especially because of the smells from the grill and frying pans. The kitchen and dining room share*

a common area. Perhaps if we put a glass partition there, customers could at least see how the chefs are working. The topic doesn't come up inside the restaurant either.

(Selçuk Restaurant)

Q4. Do you think the business model presented will make your hotel more profitable and competitive?

Yes, especially during the times the Uludağ region is losing its reputation dramatically. When we able to adapt these recommendations, I believe we will be the trail blazer in the region (Oksijen Zone Hotel).

Yes. But now, we are dealing with illegal villa/bungalow. Only when you make complaint, the necessary action is taken. Therefore, this structure affects the customer potential and profitability deeply (Gököz Natural Park).

I definitely do. I believe the Korean segment will differentiate us, especially in the foreign tourism market, with accommodations of three nights or more. We now have a clear understanding of our target audience (Artıç Hotel).

As I said, everything we discussed serves customer satisfaction, which will be our biggest competitive advantage (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel).

Yes, I think this is like the output of the question you asked earlier. **I believe that if we follow what you suggested, it will take us further** (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).

Even these things, I think, are among the most important points of branding. **Yes, it has been incredibly beneficial.** And then working on customer segmentation was also very useful in my opinion. Because while we were thinking things like, "For

example, should we bring a DJ here, should we do this or that?”, we stopped and asked:

“Wait a second, what is our target audience like?

What do they want, how do they behave, would we be doing the right thing? Is this investment the right one, is it really an investment?”

This kept coming to our minds as well, and we saw its benefits very clearly (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).

Yes, definitely—when it is implemented. During the process, the team emphasized the importance of systematically keeping a customer portfolio, and the hotel owner also acknowledged that, if this information is recorded properly, key focus areas can be identified. This will allow for more targeted advertising, which can reduce advertising costs while increasing revenue (Park Mandalin Hotel).

Yes. It is a very valuable study from this perspective (Selçuk Restaurant).

Q5. Which of the suggestions within the presented business model do you think are faster and easier to implement?

Especially I like the idea of **focusing on summer times segmentation**. We know that, we are able to attract customers on winter times even though the season starts to shorten every year. We are a pioneer in the Uludağ region which operates 12 months. This is a new development for the region and promoting this progress will be an important development for us. Also, you mentioned that making activities within the hotel is faster to do (Oksijen Zone Hotel).

Keeping Customer database could take time. But apart from that, making the video of experiences before and after and adding the comments is faster (Gököz Natural Park).

Strategies for the Balkan market and the families with children segments can be implemented more quickly and easily (Artıç Hotel).

So we discussed things like organizing themed events to boost the winter season and networking to attract authors. We actually took some initiative in this regard. For example, we invited an author who stayed here for a week. **We followed diving and sailing events, which we hadn't paid much attention to before.** We attracted customers through festivals and art exhibitions. A life coach held an event at our hotel. We partnered with a pharmaceutical company. The company closed the hotel for a few days. **Our initiatives to boost the low season were successful. It turned out well, honestly** (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel).

Among all these, we were particularly lacking in the website section. At the same time, I think these issues can be resolved very quickly. Since it is the end of the season, we are currently in a phase where we are evaluating the hotel—discussing what we are lacking, what we are doing well, and what needs to be improved. Therefore, **I believe we can make this very productive in our meetings with our own team and achieve quick results** (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).

The market here is very unstable. People keep saying things like, “That hotel has lowered its prices to this level, this one is doing that,” and so on, but we managed to stand firm there. We really struggled quite a lot. For example, even setting up our business WhatsApp account was not easy at all. But thank goodness, now we have business WhatsApp. **You had suggested that we collect the contact information**

of every guest who comes in... For example, we were a bit inconsistent with that, and we realized we need to handle it more professionally. So we set up a business WhatsApp account and started communicating through it. This was very important for me, because now we send out information about our events this way (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).

*The suggestions about **which values should be highlighted and which communication/marketing tools can be used are the fastest and easiest to implement.** In addition, aligning these elements with the hotel's website and with other websites that promote the hotel can also be done quickly (Park Mandalin Hotel).*

***QR codes, menu organisation.** It's very easy, for example. Revising the menu to be local and sustainable, vegan, vegetarian, revising the menu according to children's menus. These are things that can be done immediately at no cost (Selçuk Restaurant).*

Q6. What challenges might you encounter in implementing the presented business model? (Personnel, budget, technology, infrastructure, etc.)

***Budget, Personnel,** permits that must be obtained is critical point (Oksijen Zone Hotel).*

***Budget and Personnel** is critical point (Gököz Natural Park).*

Implementing strategies in the Middle East market may not be easy due to the current situation. Personnel issues will pose another challenge (Artıç Hotel).

*These are topics we've discussed many times before. The region has its own limitations. We want to attract customers here through our own efforts, while other hotels are doing other things. **Everyone is working individually.** But we need to work*

together; we need the support of the municipality and tourism associations, and we need more regional events. At this point, what we're doing is only going so far... We also have a scale problem. Our bed capacity cannot accommodate large events. We need to collaborate with other hotels. For example, I booked an event here, and my bed capacity is 10 people. I should be able to send the remaining 10 people to a neighboring hotel for the night. The same goes for them... but there is no such cooperation between us (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel).

Çıralı is, in terms of location, both a disadvantageous and a very advantageous area. In terms of staff and budget, it is somewhat disadvantageous. Because of this, we have to run some things online. Our team manages operations online since we are not located within the city. This sometimes creates disadvantages when it comes to finding quick solutions to problems. **We are also at a disadvantage in terms of staff selection, because our hotel is far from the city center, there is not much social life, and people may not want to live here.** Still, the area is very advantageous in many other ways. Despite these challenges, I think there will be no major issues in implementing the proposed business model (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).

I think we now need to approach **data collection** a bit differently. We should support it with a tool, like a registration card. Because the people sitting at reception can skip these steps. Sometimes they just take the ID, photocopy it, complete the formalities and hand over the room (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).

Whereas I think we need to treat this as a process which, while also taking the seriousness of communication into account, will later help that guest become one of our repeat customers (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).

That's why we're going to slightly change the way we handle check-in. Without overwhelming the guest, but in a practical way, we need to collect the necessary information and complete the process – but doing all of this can be difficult. For example, it's challenging here because the guest wants to go straight up to the room; they're always in a hurry (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).

*And then there is the **issue of finding a good chef**, because they either leave very quickly or they have habits that don't fit us, such as alcohol use. We are having a lot of problems there. For the last three months, Ms. Azize has been preparing breakfast. She even went into the kitchen as the chef because we couldn't find one (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).*

***Lack of personnel, budget, lack of collective support from the region**, restricted area of the hotel (Park Mandalin Hotel).*

*The thing that will challenge us the most right now is the **open kitchen**. An open kitchen is feasible, but it requires a long-term investment. Things to be done with the council may also be medium-term. We need to submit a written request to the council regarding these matters, as well as the issue of toilets and hygiene... (Selçuk Restaurant).*

Q7. Do you think the business model presented is sustainable for your hotel/restaurant?

***I definitely think so.** We discuss many issues among ourselves, but they remain just that. Laying these matters out before us provides us with an important roadmap for determining which ones to prioritize (Oksijen Zone Hotel).*

*Of course, I believe that the proposed business model is **sustainable** for our hotel (Gököz Natural Park).*

*I absolutely **believe** it (Artıç Hotel).*

*Whether it will continue or not depends somewhat on us. We made an effort for this period, but I'm saying **we need to be determined to continue with the activities...** (Bülbül Yuvası Hotel)*

***Yes, I do think so.** Our business is already a well-established one. I believe that this business model will be very efficient for us in the future as well (Etenna Bungalow Hotel).*

*Of course, that's actually the main thing: if you can't sustain it, it won't turn into a competitive advantage. I guess starting is the hard part. After that, I think it gets easier. Once you've taken the first step, it becomes something more sustainable. **Yes, our "awareness muscle" has developed now** (Yonca Anjelika Hotel).*

*Yes, I believe the **proposed business model is sustainable for our hotel.** Systematically keeping a customer portfolio is crucial, as it allows us to identify key focus areas and design targeted marketing activities. In addition, clearly announcing and communicating the practices we already apply—especially through our website and other platforms where the hotel is promoted—will help us consistently highlight our values and maintain a strong, competitive position over time (Park Mandalin Hotel).*

***We want it to be sustainable.** But the attitude of certain parties, such as the local council, will also shape this. (Selçuk Restaurant)*

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

In the report, all of the studies conducted on the hotels are given briefly. Firstly, the business model innovation methodology has been explained. In addition, the tools that have been used in the process of business model innovation are explained. Secondly, the business model analysis and innovation activities are clarified for each hotel. The implementation part has been divided into two phases which are pilot (first round) and second round. According to the pilot round implementation, a brief table has been given in order to explain whether the business models of the pilot companies have been innovated.

In the second round implementation, the other hotels and restaurants are examined and new business models are suggested. In addition, the implementation strategies are given. Then, the impact assessment methodology is explained. It is designed as a two-stage methodology. Given the limited time between implementation and reporting, a short-term impact assessment strategy was adopted, combining micro KPI tracking, and brief interviews. This rapid assessment approach allows for early insight into model applicability and initial outcomes, while setting a basis for future evaluation. The most realistic and efficient way forward is to conduct a short-term but meaningful impact assessment. Both in early stage indicators and semi-structured interviews, it is generally seen that innovated business models of the companies have been successful according to the obtained impact assessment results. This indicates that business model innovation methodology has a great potential for hospitality industry.